

Impact of particle size distribution on the behaviour of lithium-ion batteries under dynamic operation

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Abstract

Physics-based electrochemical models are widely used to predict lithium-ion battery (LIB) behaviour under realistic operating conditions, where simplified laboratory profiles are insufficient. In this study, three models of different complexity were implemented and compared: the Doyle–Fuller–Newman (DFN) model, the Many-Particle Model (MPM), and the Many-Particle Doyle–Fuller–Newman model (MP-DFN). The models were parameterized using available datasets and adjusted to best represent a commercial LG M50LT cylindrical cell and validated against experimental data from constant-current/constant-voltage charging and discharge under the Worldwide Harmonised Light Vehicle Test Cycle (WLTC). The results show that whilst all models reproduce the overall voltage response, the many-particle formulations capture dynamic behaviour more faithfully, particularly during WLTC discharge, where the particle size distribution strongly influences predictive accuracy. These improvements are accompanied by higher computational demands, but the study provides new insight into the role of particle-level heterogeneity under realistic automotive conditions and offers guidance for selecting suitable modelling approaches depending on application needs.

Graphical abstract

Keywords Electrochemical modelling · Lithium-ion battery · Particle size distribution · DFN model · Dynamic operation · Simulation

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Introduction

Battery energy storage systems are essential in the transition towards low-carbon energy and transport systems. Their role in mitigating the intermittency of renewable energy sources and supporting the electrification of mobility has made them integral to modern decarbonisation strategies. Amongst various energy storage technologies, lithium-ion batteries (LIBs)

remain the dominant choice due to their high energy and power density, long cycle life, and ongoing cost reductions [1–3].

As LIBs become increasingly integrated into real-world applications—particularly in electric vehicles (EVs)—the need for accurate performance prediction under dynamic operating conditions is growing. Electrochemical models based on physical principles offer a robust framework for understanding battery behaviour at multiple scales, from particle-level diffusion to full-cell voltage response [4]. These models are also essential for optimising control strategies, ensuring safety, and extending battery lifetime.

One of the most established modelling approaches is the Doyle–Fuller–Newman (DFN) model, which provides a spatially resolved description of mass and charge transport within a battery cell [5]. However, many implementations of DFN and other physics-based models rely on the simplifying assumption that all active material particles within an electrode are of uniform size. In contrast, real electrodes exhibit significant microstructural heterogeneity, including broad particle size distributions (PSDs) that can influence local reaction kinetics, effective diffusion lengths, and mechanical stresses [6].

This heterogeneity becomes particularly relevant under high-rate, dynamic conditions, where variations in particle size lead to unequal utilisation and potential reaction imbalance. Over time, such effects may accelerate localised degradation phenomena, such as lithium plating or loss of active material. Addressing these complexities requires models that can incorporate realistic microstructural features without becoming computationally prohibitive [7].

In this work, three physics-based models of increasing complexity were implemented and compared: the classical DFN model, the Many-Particle Model (MPM), and the Many-Particle DFN (MP-DFN). All models were parameterized using the available PyBaMM datasets for LG M50 cells [8] and subsequently adjusted according to the data from the literature to represent the cylindrical LG M50LT cell

[9]. The simulations were validated using experimental data obtained under the Worldwide Harmonised Light Vehicle Test Cycle (WLTC), a dynamic current profile representative of real driving conditions.

The primary objective is to evaluate how incorporating particle size distribution affects model accuracy in voltage prediction, with particular emphasis on realistic driving conditions such as the WLTC, rather than only on standard CC-CV laboratory profiles. This perspective highlights the relevance of the study for performance forecasting and degradation modelling under conditions closer to real automotive operation, with the potential for future extension using available degradation submodels in PyBaMM.

Results

The simulation results were validated by comparison with the experimental data. Figure 1 shows the voltage response of all three models along with the measured data during constant-current/constant-voltage (CCCV) charging, including the subsequent relaxation phase. All models captured the voltage trend with reasonable accuracy and without significant deviations. The largest discrepancies appear around the transition between the constant current and constant voltage stages, where the models slightly overestimate the cell voltage.

This behaviour can be attributed to the modelling approach used: the current profile obtained from the experiment was applied as a boundary condition, rather than prescribing the charging regime explicitly. As a result, a slight shift in the timing of the transition may occur, leading to small differences in the predicted voltage response.

Figure 2 presents the comparison between simulated and experimental voltage profiles during cell discharge under the WLTC driving profile. For all three models evaluated (DFN, MPM, and MP-DFN), the predicted voltage tends to

Fig. 1 Comparison of simulated and measured voltage during charging

Fig. 2 Comparison of simulated and measured voltage during WLTC discharge for: **a** DFN model, **b** MPM model, **c** MP-DFN model

Table 1 RMSE between simulated and measured voltage curves and computational time for each model

Model	RMSE/mV		Computational time/s	
	Charging	WLTC	Charging	WLTC
DFN	8.6	18.7	20.8	332.5
MPM	8.9	16.8	23.3	281.7
MP-DFN	10.2	15.9	320.7	7948.2

be slightly higher than the measured values for the majority of the profile.

Several factors may contribute to this discrepancy. Firstly, the input current profile used in the simulations was interpolated from the experimental data, which may introduce minor deviations. In addition, uncertainties in model parameters—particularly in the open-circuit voltage (OCV) curves and diffusion coefficients—can also influence the accuracy, as they represent a mix of values from different literature sources that may not fully capture the specific characteristics of the tested cells.

Each graph includes a zoomed-in section around 50% state of charge (SoC), where the differences between model and experiment are more pronounced. Notably, the more advanced many-particle models (MPM and MP-DFN) exhibit smaller deviations compared to the baseline DFN model. This highlights the benefit of incorporating particle size distribution into the modelling framework, especially under dynamic load conditions.

The predictive accuracy of each electrochemical model was quantified using the root-mean-squared error (RMSE) for both charging and WLTC discharge simulations. The corresponding RMSE values, along with the computational time required for each model, are summarised in Table 1, enabling a direct comparison of their accuracy and complexity.

During the constant-current/constant-voltage (CCCV) charging simulations, all three models showed comparable accuracy with RMSE values below 11 mV. The DFN model achieved the lowest RMSE (8.6 mV) and also required the shortest computational time (20.8 s), highlighting its efficiency for standard operating conditions. In contrast, the MP-DFN model exhibited a slightly higher deviation (10.2 mV) and significantly longer runtime (320.7 s), reflecting the added computational burden of incorporating particle size distribution. These results suggest that, under simple and stable conditions such as CCCV charging, the increased model complexity may not lead to significant improvements in accuracy.

In the case of WLTC discharge simulations, where the current profile is highly dynamic, the advantages of including particle-level heterogeneity became more evident. The MP-DFN model yielded the lowest RMSE (15.9 mV), outperforming both MPM (16.8 mV) and DFN (18.7 mV),

although at the cost of a drastically higher computational time (more than 2 h). This indicates that whilst simpler models may suffice for basic scenarios, more detailed formulations are better suited, accuracy-wise, for realistic driving profiles. Overall, the results demonstrate that incorporating particle size distribution improves voltage prediction fidelity under complex conditions, though with a substantial increase in computational demands.

Discussion

Comparison of DFN, MPM, and MP-DFN models not only demonstrates differences in predictive accuracy and computational efficiency, but also highlights their broader implications for practical applications. The ability of many-particle models to capture particle size heterogeneity provides more reliable voltage predictions under highly dynamic driving conditions. Such improvements may translate into better estimation of available energy and, consequently, more accurate range prediction for EVs. For stationary energy storage, improved fidelity could reduce the need for conservative safety margins, thus increasing the usable effective capacity of the system.

Another important aspect is the potential of advanced electrochemical models in degradation studies. Although degradation mechanisms were not explicitly included in this work, the implemented MP-DFN framework is compatible with degradation submodels available in PyBaMM and other modelling platforms, allowing for future extensions. This approach has already been used in previous studies to investigate ageing-related phenomena such as lithium plating or the loss of active material [10, 11]. By enabling spatial resolution across the electrode and incorporating particle-level heterogeneity, the MP-DFN model allows for the analysis of concentration gradients and local current densities, which are directly linked to such degradation processes. These capabilities can support the development of more mechanistic lifetime models and offer valuable input for strategies aiming to extend battery safety and durability.

At the same time, the results reaffirm the importance of balancing model fidelity and computational complexity. Although high-fidelity models provide the richest physical information, their use in real-time automotive applications is limited by their computational cost. Reduced-order approaches, surrogate models, or hybrid frameworks may therefore be needed to bridge the gap between detailed physics and practical applicability.

Finally, this study also underscores the potential of open-source tools, such as PyBaMM, for both academic research and industrial development. By making complex physics-based models widely accessible, such platforms foster

Fig. 3 Current profile based on WLTC driving cycle

collaboration and accelerate the translation of modelling insights into practical use cases in the automotive sector.

Conclusion

This work compared three physics-based models of lithium-ion batteries—DFN, MPM, and MP-DFN—under both standard charging and dynamic driving conditions. Whilst the many-particle extensions improved agreement with experimental voltage data, particularly during WLTC discharge, these gains came at the expense of substantially higher computational demand. The study therefore underlines a central trade-off in battery modelling: achieving higher fidelity by accounting for particle heterogeneity versus retaining the efficiency required for practical applications.

Beyond the accuracy of benchmarking, the results also illustrate the complementary role of different models. The DFN remains suitable for fast simulations and control-oriented studies, the MPM offers a compromise between accuracy and efficiency, and the MP-DFN provides the highest level of detail for high-fidelity simulations such as parameter identification or degradation studies. Future progress will likely depend on the development of hybrid or reduced-order approaches that preserve the improved accuracy of many-particle models whilst mitigating their computational demand.

Methods

Battery cells

The experimental data used for model validation utilize commercial 21700 cylindrical lithium-ion cells (LG M50LT, 5 Ah) with a nickel–manganese–cobalt (NMC) cathode and graphite anode.

Battery tests

Charging

The cell was initially charged in the constant current (CC) mode at 1.6 A until the voltage reached 4.15 V, followed by a constant voltage (CV) mode until the current dropped to 0.48 A, which corresponded to charging about 95% SoC. Following this, a relaxation period of 5 min was applied.

Discharging

The discharge process consisted of applying a current profile based on the WLTC, as shown in Fig. 3. Each WLTC sequence was followed by a 10 s rest period, after which the profile was repeated. This procedure was carried out multiple times until the cell voltage dropped below 3 V. A final relaxation phase lasting 5 min was applied after discharge.

Battery modelling

All battery simulations were performed using the open-source Python Battery Mathematical Modelling (PyBaMM) package, version 25.4.3. The simulations were executed on an HP Z2 Tower G9 workstation equipped with an Intel Core i9-13900 processor (13th generation, 2.00 GHz), 32 GB of DDR5 RAM (4400 MHz), and running Windows 11 Pro. This setup ensured sufficient computational capacity for the implementation and comparison of advanced physics-based models under dynamic current profiles. All models were parameterized using the Chen2020 dataset [8] and adapted to reflect the geometry of a commercial LG M50LT cylindrical cell [9].

Doyle–Fuller–Newman model

The Doyle–Fuller–Newman model, also referred to as the pseudo-two-dimensional (P2D) or Newman model, is one of the most widely used physics-based frameworks for lithium-ion batteries. It assumes spherical electrode particles and one-dimensional through-cell geometry, which enables efficient numerical solutions whilst still capturing essential transport and kinetic phenomena.

The model couples (i) lithium diffusion within electrode particles, (ii) charge transport in the solid and electrolyte phases, and (iii) interfacial kinetics at the particle–electrolyte interface. The governing equations can be summarised as follows:

1. Solid-phase diffusion (particle):

$$\frac{\partial c_{s,k}}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 D_k(c_{s,k}) \frac{\partial c_{s,k}}{\partial r} \right), \quad 0 \leq r \leq R_k \quad (1)$$

with boundary conditions

$$\left. \frac{\partial c_{s,k}}{\partial r} \right|_{r=0} = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$-D_k \left. \frac{\partial c_{s,k}}{\partial r} \right|_{r=R_k} = \frac{j_k}{F}, \quad (3)$$

where $c_{s,k}$ is the concentration of lithium in solid-phase in electrode k (n is negative, p is positive), t is the time, r is the radial coordinate inside a spherical particle, D_k is the solid-phase diffusion coefficient, R_k is the particle radius in electrode k , j_k is the interfacial current density in electrode k , and F is Faraday constant. This current density is linked to degradation phenomena such as lithium plating or loss of active material.

2. Solid-phase potential:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\sigma_k^{eff} \frac{\partial \phi_{s,k}}{\partial x} \right) = -a_{s,k} F j_k, \quad (4)$$

where x is the spatial coordinate along the cell thickness (negative electrode – separator – positive electrode direction), σ_k^{eff} is the effective electronic conductivity, $\phi_{s,k}$ is the solid-phase potential, and $a_{s,k}$ is the specific surface area of the active material in electrode k .

3. Electrolyte mass balance:

$$\varepsilon(x) \frac{\partial c_e}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(D_e^{eff}(c_e) \frac{\partial c_e}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{1-t^+}{F} a_s(x) j, \quad (5)$$

where $\varepsilon(x)$ is the porosity at position x , c_e is the electrolyte lithium-ion concentration, D_e^{eff} is the effective electrolyte diffusion coefficient, and t^+ is the lithium-ion transference number.

4. Electrolyte potential:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\kappa^{eff}(c_e) \frac{\partial \phi_e}{\partial x} - 2\kappa^{eff}(c_e)(1-t^+) \frac{RT}{F} \frac{\partial \ln c_e}{\partial x} \right) = a_s(x) F j, \quad (6)$$

where $\kappa^{eff}(c_e)$ is the effective ionic conductivity of the electrolyte, ϕ_e is the electrolyte potential, R is the universal gas constant, and T is the absolute temperature.

5. Interfacial kinetics (symmetric Butler–Volmer):

$$j_k = 2j_{0,k} \sinh \left(\frac{F\eta_k}{2RT} \right), \quad \eta_k = \phi_{s,k} - \phi_e - U_k(c_{s,k}^{surf}) \quad (7)$$

where $j_{0,k}$ is the exchange current density in electrode, η_k is the surface overpotential in electrode k , and U_k is the open-circuit potential (OCV) of electrode k . This symmetric formulation of the Butler–Volmer equation assumes equal charge transfer coefficients for the anodic and cathodic reactions, i.e. $\alpha_a = \alpha_c = 0.5$. This simplification leads to the use of the hyperbolic sine function and is commonly adopted in electrochemical modelling tools such as PyBaMM.

Together, these equations describe the spatio-temporal evolution of lithium concentration, electrolyte composition, and potentials within the cell. The terminal voltage is obtained as the potential difference between the current collectors [5, 12–14].

Many-Particle model

The Many-Particle model is an extension of the Single-Particle model (SPM), designed to account for particle size variability whilst maintaining the assumption of spherical particles in each electrode. Instead of a single representative

radius, MPM represents the electrode as a continuum of particles with radii sampled from a distribution, typically weighted by surface area. Although spatial variations in the electrolyte and through-cell direction are still neglected, the model resolves diffusion and reaction kinetics across a range of particle sizes. This provides a more realistic approximation of electrode behaviour than that of SPM, capturing phenomena influenced by particle heterogeneity, such as rate-dependent voltage response and capacity utilisation.

For each particle radius R , the lithium concentration evolves according to Fick's law:

$$\frac{\partial c(R, t)}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 D(R, c) \frac{\partial c}{\partial r} \right), \quad 0 \leq r \leq R, \quad (8)$$

with boundary conditions identical to the DFN formulation. The interfacial current density for each particle is given by a Butler–Volmer expression. The total interfacial current density, $j_{tot}(t)$, is then obtained by integrating the local current density $j(R, t)$ over the particle size distribution $f(R)$ [10]:

$$j_{tot}(t) = \int_0^\infty j(R, t) f(R) dR. \quad (9)$$

Many-Particle Doyle–Fuller–Newman model

The Many-Particle Doyle–Fuller–Newman model extends the DFN framework by incorporating a distribution of particle sizes at each point along the electrode thickness. Whilst the standard DFN assumes that all electrode particles are identical in size, this assumption does not reflect the true microstructure of real electrodes, where particles vary in size and shape. The MP-DFN therefore introduces an additional dimension that spans across the particle size, allowing the model to account for a range of diffusion behaviours and interfacial reactions associated with different particle radii.

For each particle of radius R in electrode k , the lithium concentration evolves according to:

$$\frac{\partial c_{s,k}(x, r, t, R)}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 D_k(c_{s,k}) \frac{\partial c_{s,k}}{\partial r} \right), \quad 0 \leq r \leq R \quad (10)$$

with boundary conditions identical to those in the DFN model.

The total interfacial current density is obtained by integrating the particle size distribution $f(R)$:

$$j_{tot,k}(x, t) = \int_0^\infty j_k(x, t, R) f(R) dR, \quad (11)$$

where $j(x, t, R)$ is the local current density given by the Butler–Volmer equation. Electrolyte concentration and potential are governed by the same conservation equations as in the DFN but now are coupled to $j_{tot}(x, t)$.

As a result, MP-DFN provides a more realistic representation of heterogeneous electrode structures whilst still assuming spherical particles. This approach enables better prediction of certain phenomena, such as lithium concentration gradients or voltage response under dynamic conditions, and has been shown to improve agreement with experimental results in some cases [11, 15].

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Declarations

Conflict of interest The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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